

The Significance of Philosophy in Peace and Conflict Thinking and Practice

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Introduction

Peace and conflicts are two incompatible issues that have been with humanity since the inception of humanity. While conflicts are inevitable in any given society, peace is desirable by all and sundry. Every society is, therefore, making every effort to reduce conflicts and promote peaceful co-existence among the members of the society. In order to achieve this, many philosophies are formulated and adhered to by many sectors of the society. The aim of this paper is to rationally justify the significance of philosophy in peace and conflict thinking and practice. The paper will briefly give various definitions of philosophy, peace, and conflict, and then give some reasons why philosophy is significant in peace and conflict thinking and practice.

Philosophy

Literally, the term “philosophy” means “love of wisdom” or simply “pursuit of knowledge”. The word “philosophy” comes from two Greek words, that is, “*phileo*” (love) and “*sophia*” (wisdom) which become one word “*philosophia*”. This etymology has made the term to be defined, described, and used in different ways from time immemorial till date. An online dictionary definition of philosophy is, “The study of the fundamental nature of knowledge, reality, and existence, especially when

considered as an academic discipline.”¹ From this writer’s findings, philosophers do not make attempts to have a definite definition of philosophy. Most of them rather describe philosophy in line with their areas of thought. Some scholars even gave five different meanings of philosophy in their attempts to define the word.² However, one can say that philosophy is a way of deeper thinking about a particular subject. So, philosophy of peace and conflict studies is thinking deeply about peace and conflicts, and this thinking can bring about a better peaceful coexistence of people in the society.

Peace

Various groups of people have defined peace in various ways. Simply, peace can be seen as concord, or harmony and tranquility within oneself, among two or more people, or in the society at large. Peace can also be described as the existence of social justice, and the absence of war, violence, and conflict. Another definition of peace is “freedom from disturbance, tranquility, absence of war, fear, conflict, anxiety, suffering, violence, and about peaceful co-existence.”³ Peace has been described as “an occurrence of harmony characterized by lack of violence, conflicting behaviours and freedom from fear or violence.... [It] means the following: A state of quite or tranquility; freedom from disturbance or agitation; general order or tranquility; freedom from violence or riot; a state of reconciliation after strife or enmity.”⁴

¹ “Philosophy”. *Oxford English and Spanish Dictionary, Thesaurus, and Spanish to English Translator*. <https://www.lexico.com/definition/philosophy>. Accessed 25 August 2020.

² What Is Philosophy? http://eddiejackson.net/web_documents/What%20Is%20Philosophy.pdf. Accessed 6 May 2023.

³ Yisa Jonah, Yusuf Abdullahi, and Yemisi Olawale. “Conflict Peace and Security: The Nigeria Experience”. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. Volume: 4, Issue: 12, December 2018, 78-89., 80.

⁴ Patrick Enaigbe and Nicholas Igbinoghene. “Challenges of Managing and Planning Peace Education and Peace Culture in Nigeria”. *African Research Review*. Vol. 10(4), Serial No.43, September, 2016: 83-92., 84-85.

Against the backdrop that “we often recognize [peace] by its absence,”⁵ positive and negative peace have been identified and differentiated. Negative peace is the absence of violence, pessimistic, curative, and peace not always by peaceful means, while positive peace is structural integration, optimistic, preventive, and peace by peaceful means.⁶ It is the opinion of some scholars that “the word ‘PEACE’ has a clear meaning for most people, [but] ‘peaceful act’ and ‘peaceful individual’ can have different interpretations.”⁷ These scholars went further,

the peaceful act is an act that brings humans closer to peace. And the peaceful individual is a person who is at peace. Such an individual has overcome his internal conflicts and has freed himself from other conflicts.... However, a peaceful person, who is at peace, does not have such inner brakes to stop his transcendent movement, and his mental energy is not concentrated on dealing with such conflicts.⁸

Conflict

It is difficult to give a precise definition of conflict because it is multifarious and dependent upon its context or usage,⁹ and peace researchers do not agree on its meaning.¹⁰ Many scholars prefer to describe conflict with scenarios rather than simply

⁵ Charles Webel and Johan Galtung (eds.). *Handbook of Peace and Conflict Studies*. (Oxon: Routledge, 2007). <https://www.mkgandhi.org/ebks/handbook-of-peace-and-conflict-studies.pdf>, 6. Accessed October 12, 2019.

⁶ Catholic Relief Services. *Peacebuilding Fundamentals: Participant’s Manual*. (Baltimore, MD: Catholic Relief Services, 2018). Accessed November 19, 2019 https://www.crs.org/sites/default/files/tools-research/peacebuilding_fundamentals_manual.pdf, 45.

⁷ Mohammad Ali Taheri and Maryam Dehghan. “Definition of Peace and Its Different Types as Approached by Halqeh Mysticism”. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 114 (2014) 56–61., 56-57.

⁸ Taheri and Dehghan. “Definition of Peace”.

⁹ Shawn Young. “The Nature of Conflict: Interpret Perception of Conflict”. Accessed November 4, 2019 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315828521_The_Nature_of_Conflict_Interpret_Perception_of_Conflict, 1.

¹⁰ Jonah, et al. “Conflict Peace and Security”, 79.

define it. So, some scholars have described conflict as “a struggle or contest between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals.”¹¹ Another similar definition of conflict is: “disagreement or struggle between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values or goals.”¹²

Conflict can emerge at any time. In fact, conflict is normal. It is unavoidable. It is part of human nature. The world is a violent place full of many crises, conflicts, and wars.¹³ These conflicts arise because of various political, economic, religious, marital, personal, and other reasons. Human survival in this world hinges on how we manage the various features of conflict that are fuelled by these seemingly incompatible interests and values.¹⁴

Four different types of conflicts have been identified thus: intra-personal (conflict within an individual), intra-group (conflict within a group), inter-personal (conflict between two or more people), and Inter-group (conflict between two or more groups).¹⁵ Conflicts can be caused by a variety of things. It may be a conflict of interests when two or more parties want to achieve something from a different situation with high compatibility of goals and needs; it may be a conflict of needs centred around essential things one must have like food, water, shelter, clothing, and security; it may be a conflict of values, that is, clash over ideas, morality, religion or beliefs, human right standards, and tradition; it may be a conflict of identities like race (being a member of

¹¹ Emily Pia and Thomas Diez. “Conflict and Human Rights: A Theoretical Framework”. Accessed November 4, 2019

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/bd11/ded6bae9efb9feee558b1441f62880b449ae.pdf>, 2.

¹² Catholic Relief Services. *Peacebuilding Fundamentals: Participant’s Manual*. (Baltimore, MD: Catholic Relief Services, 2018), 16.

¹³ *Conflict Barometer 2015*, a publication of The Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research (HIK) at the Department of Political Science, University of Heidelberg (Accessed June 23 2016 from http://www.hiik.de/de/konfliktbarometer/pdf/ConflictBarometer_2015.pdf) analysed disputes, non-violent crises, violent crises, limited wars, and wars in the world in the year 2015.

¹⁴ Ho-Won Jeong. *Understanding Conflict and Conflict Analysis*. (London: SAGE Publications Ltd. 2008), 3.

¹⁵ Catholic Relief Services. *Peacebuilding Fundamentals*, 19.

a minority), sex (being a man or a woman), nationality, tribe, and the likes; it may be ideological or worldview conflicts like a disagreement over political ideologies (e.g. communism, capitalism, and holy war); it may be conflicts of esteem and judgment especially when it has to do with decision making.¹⁶

Four basic stages of conflict have been affirmed. These stages are “latent, manifest, crisis and de-escalation stages.”¹⁷ Conflict is at the latent stage when it is yet to surface, but there is a rising consciousness of the conflict. Conflict is in the manifest stage when its face starts with low-level violence. Conflict at the crisis stage represents its highest point with unguarded antagonism between the conflicting parties. The last stage, the de-escalation stage is divided into two stages: the improvement and the transformation stages. These stages are when a third party intervenes in the conflict and the conflicting parties start to recognize the views and concerns of the other party, and efforts are being made to change the approaches of the conflicting parties to the conflict thereby paving ways for conflict transformation.¹⁸

Significance of Philosophy in Peace and Conflict Thinking and Practice

As concluded in the brief definition of philosophy above, philosophy is important in peace and conflict thinking and practice because it helps to think deeply on how to avoid or reduce conflict and promote peace thereby having a more peaceful coexistence of people in the society. Thinking deeply about peace and conflicts enables one to find out the issues that are making conflicts to emanate and escalate. It also enables one to

¹⁶ Cornelia Brinkmann. *Steps for Peace: Working Manual for Peace Building and Conflict Management* (Kabul: German Development Service, 2006). Accessed November 23, 2019 <http://www.steps-for-peace.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/Brinkmann-Manual-Steps-for-peace.pdf>, 32.

¹⁷ Oluwaseun O. Afolabi. “Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Tool for Managing Leadership Conflict in a Church”. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, Volume 12, Number 4, 2018, 44.

¹⁸ Afolabi. “Alternative Dispute Resolution”.

find out ways to discourage these issues and de-escalate conflicts and encourage people to live peacefully in the society. These deeper thoughts have enabled scholars and other stakeholders to come up with many theories that can help in achieving a more peaceful coexistence of people and reduce conflicts in the society.

Conclusion

Inasmuch as conflicts are inevitable in any given society, in order to reduce these conflicts and promote peaceful coexistence of people in the society, people should devote their time and energy to thinking deeply and formulate some theories. These theories should be translated into practice. This is the significance of the philosophy of peace and conflict thinking and practice.